

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO SCHOOL-AGE CHILDREN

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Annotation: This article describes the methods, techniques and teaching foreign languages to school-age children in an effective and easy way with detailed examples

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Teaching foreign languages to children, especially to young learners, is both a complex and fun process. Before teaching them a certain language, teachers are first required to be polite and kind, a person who loves their profession. It takes a lot of hard work to teach them easily in such situations. If the following important and effective methods of language learning are used, language organization will undoubtedly become the most interesting and interesting activity for them.

First of all, we use simple words for the beginning part in teaching foreign languages to young organizers, and memorizing these words by repeating them as much as possible gives good results. For example, "Hello, how are you?" and every time we encourage students to ask such questions before class or tell them to use them in their daily lives with their friends, it gradually becomes a child's habit. Such words can be used not only for greetings, but also on various topics. Not only teachers but also parents can make a small contribution to this work. They can also use simple everyday words when spending time with their little ones. As an example, by saying, "Give me a red container," you can create an understanding of the translation of colors in the child's mind. This process may not seem easy to some parents, but in today's information-communication era, everyone can download different apps to smart gadgets and use them to perform such processes.

Second, if a teacher has to work with younger learners, the teacher is required to think like them and be as positive and emotional as they are. Even well-known speakers have said that you cannot convey information correctly without knowing and feeling the person you are trying to convey (from a public speech). Therefore, such an action requires at least some psychological and acting skills from you. As mentioned above, they have a good effect on remembering and memorizing each new word in the form of more games, scenes, and various small competitions.

If we teach the lessons in a simple way without any fun games, such a lesson can be very boring for them. Therefore, before each teacher begins their lessons, the teacher is required to have a good lesson plan and decorate each lesson process with music, pictures, and games related to the lesson. As an example, if we simply take the topic of "feeling," explaining to them the events that take place in that situation with facial expressions and using their acting skills will be well remembered by the students.

Repetition is the most effective way to memorize new words. It will be useful not only for children, but also for students of all ages. Identify 3-4 different repetition exercises that you need, of course, they should be different, children are quick learners and quick forgetters, and repetition can be a good solution to such problems. For example, in memorizing a word, we say it in the form of a game, first loudly and slowly, then gradually, in a low voice, and finally in a whisper, repeating the words to them together with the students. In this way, the word is repeated five times in the children's memory, and later children are able to understand those words even though they are pronounced differently in different pronunciations. At the same time, neglecting or making too much noise when working with students can have a detrimental effect on the learning process. Teachers are required to use these in every necessary part of the lesson so that at such times, they can even take steps to calm and regulate them in the form of a game. For example, if there is a sign of disorder during the lesson, we should immediately use the acting skills of the teachers and draw their attention to the fact that they say, "Oh, kids, there are bees flying in our classroom, let's hear their voices." From a scientific point of view, such a process is called "ice break" and one of the methods of ice break: where we all count together, "1..2..3..4..5... now lets sit nicely". Repeating such processes gives them the ability to be disciplined. Then, of course, the teacher will be able to continue the lesson. One of the golden secrets of communicating with children is not to be rude to them at all. Treating them badly is the worst way to go because young children don't do what they don't like. Therefore, it is the most important rule to show kindness to them in the first place, and one of the most important and necessary ways is to keep as many students as possible active during the lesson. This method is called student center in science. This method has many advantages and is effective for learners of all ages. First of all, this method requires independence, more effort to make students active. In this way, the student will be able to better understand the topics. We can cite several examples of such methods. For example, we get a story or text that is about a certain topic. When we read the words we have memorized, we are not the teacher, but we ask the students what it is, or we explain the words we want to ask with the circumstances and tell them, "What was the word, kids?" we re-apply or say that it works as a group work by giving dialogues on any topic. In this way, they are organized to work as a team in society in the future. Such student center methods are very useful and necessary for today's modern educational programs.

List of used literature: "How to teach English to young learners Amazon.com," Teaching young learner English theory to Practice ", " National Geographic Learning / Heinle, Cengage Learning, 2013 ", " Teaching young learners in ESL and EFL settings National Geographic Learning / Cengage Learning "